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THE ELEMENTS OF PROFITABILITY FOR INDIAN PETROLEUM COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT

This paper uses several measures of profitability to examine the determinants of profitability for the Indian petroleum companies i.e. Bharat petroleum corporation limited (BPCL), Indian Oil Corporation limited (IOCL), Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Limited (HPCL), and Cairn India. The purpose of this study is to observe the association among the Activity ratio or Turnover ratio and profitability of the Indian Petroleum companies over the preceding six years period from 2010 – 2015. These ratio analyze have enormous possibilities to help organizations in improving their revenue generation capability as well as reducing of expenses. I have used five ratio as a variables for the analyses i.e. Inventory Turnover Ratio (ITR); Debtors’ Turnover Ratio (DTR); Working Capital Turnover (WCT); Total Assets Turnover Ratio (TAT) and Profit Margin (PM). Profitability as a dependent variable is represented by profit margin (PM) while Activity ratio or Turnover ratio stands as ITR, DTR, WCT, and TAT for independent variables. Secondary data were obtained from the financial statements, and income statement of the certain petroleum companies’ financial statement. The data have been analyzed with descriptive research technique and multiple regressions to find out the link between the variables. There is a negative relationship between working capital turnover and the profitability of the petroleum companies. On the other hand, total asset turnover is positively associated with profitability of petroleum companies. Indian oil companies should also try and boost the asset turnover by using different persuasive strategies and make sure the equipment and wealth are helping you produce more revenue than to spend on maintenances.

Keywords: Profitability Determinants, Petroleum Industry, Financial Exploration, Inventory Turnover Ratio, Debtors’ Turnover Ratio

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial analysis is mostly done to compare the growth, profitability and financial reliability of the industry or the firms by identifying the information enclosed in the financial statements. Financial analysis is done to identify the financial strengths and weaknesses of the industry or the firm by properly establishing relationship between the items of financial statement and income statement. It helps in better understanding of company's financial situation. Pandey (2010) added ratio analysis is a powerful tool of financial analysis. By taking ratio, one can measure profitability, marketability and performance of any organization and firm and can also do compare among firms and industry.

The rest of the article is systematized as trails. The following segment, literature review has been added to give cherished insights and the views of other researchers in various countries. This is trailed by a section which provides the selected technique to the oil companies in India. Next follows the conjectural and empirical significances of this approach for ratios and the question of the possible quantity bias in the indirect estimation of the independent variables are examined in this section. Finally, the paper presents a discussion of the results, and conclusion of the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Charalambidis & Papadopoulos (2010), elaborates four financial distress prediction models for Greek firms are tested. Relevant analysis is based on a sample of 37 financially distressed (18 listed and 19 non-listed) and 226 non-distressed (48 listed and 178 non-listed) firms. The superiority of a particular model relates to its predictive accuracy and expected loss of misclassification errors in a range of likely values for the prior probability of financial distress and the cost ratio of Types 1 and 2 errors.) No single model can be considered absolutely appropriate to predict the financial distress of Greek firms as superiority of models differs between non-listed and listed firms.

(Enekwe Chinedu Innocent, 2013), examined the relationship between the financial ratio analysis and profitability of the Nigerian Pharmaceutical industry over the past eleven (11) years period from 2001 – 2011. The results revealed that debtors' turnover ratio, creditors' velocity and total assets turnover ratio have no significant relationship on the profitability of the company while only inventory turnover ratio shows a significant relationship with profitability.

(Bansal, Kar, & Mishra, 2016), conducted a comparative financial performance analysis between Indian and global oil companies during 2010-2014. Result reveals that the current ratio is the highest for the Cairn India, which shows good short term financial strength of the company. They have found that British Petroleum (BP) and Royal Dutch Shell Plc (RDS) have better return on assets and shareholder's equity but it has been depreciating for the period 2012-14. Over the period of 2010-2014, the Indian Oil PSU's had generated more earning per shares to

their shareholder's investment compared to Cairn India, British Petroleum and Royal Dutch Shell.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study makes use of the financial ratio analysis using the blended frameworks of Brigham and Houston (2009) and Fraser and Ormiston (2004). As applied in this study, to test the relationship between solvency ratio and profit margin.

3.1 Research Problem and Objectives

This research paper aims to test the significant relationship between solvency ratios i.e. with the profitability of Indian oil companies during 2010 -2015. As a research procedure, the researcher obtained the audited financial statements for the six periods (2010 – 2015) of the selected oil and gas companies from 'Prowess' database and company's website. Financial analysis for Indian companies is based on the data for the financial year ending on 31 March. Financial information necessary for financial ratios were derived from these financial statements. These were then summarized and processed to come up with comparative financial ratios that were used in the analysis phase.

Moreover, this study specifically aims to meet the following objectives:

1. To determine the activity, and profitability ratio.
2. To determine industry figures, and peculiarities of the oil and gas sector in India.
3. To find out the relationship between activity ratio and profitability of the selected oil and gas companies.

3.2 Measures for Variables

The variables used in the study have been taken from (bansal, 2014) as described below.

3.2.1 Profit margin

A ratio of profitability calculated as profit after tax by net sales. Profit margin is very useful when comparing companies in similar industries. A higher profit margin indicates a more profitable company that has better control over its costs compared to its competitors. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Profit Margin} = \text{Profit after tax} / \text{Net sales} \dots\dots\dots (1.1)$$

3.2.2 Inventory turnover ratio

A ratio showing how many times a company's inventory is sold and replaced over a period. The days in the period can then be divided by the inventory turnover formula to calculate the days it takes to sell the inventory on hand or "inventory turnover days. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Inventory turnover ratio} = \text{Cost of goods sold} / \text{Average inventory} \dots\dots\dots (1.2)$$

3.2.3 Debtor turnover ratio

An activity or turnover ratio which is calculated as credit sales by average debtors. A high debtor turnover ratio is not good for a company. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Debtor turnover ratio} = \text{Credit sales} / \text{Average debtors} \dots\dots\dots (1.3)$$

3.2.4 Working capital turnover

A measurement comparing the depletion of working capital to the generation of sales over a given period is known as working capital turnover. This provides some useful information as to how effectively a company is using its working capital to generate sales. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Working capital turnover} = \text{Sales} / \text{Working capital} \dots\dots\dots (1.4)$$

3.2.5 Total asset turnover

It can be calculate as net sales divided by total assets. This is a measure of how well assets are being used to produce revenue. A high total asset turnover is beneficial for a company. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Total asset turnover} = \text{Net sales} / \text{Total assets} \dots\dots\dots(1.5)$$

3.3 Hypothesis Development

Null Hypotheses: H₀: There is no statistically significant relationship between Activity ratio and the profitability of Indian oil companies.

Inventory turnover ratio

H₁: There is a negative significant relationship between inventory turnover ratio and the unit of profitability.

Debtor turnover ratio

H₂: There is a negative substantial relationship between debtor turnover ratio and the amount of profitability.

Working capital turnover

H₃: There is a negative significant association between working capital turnover ratio and the level of profitability.

Total asset turnover

H₄: There is a positive significant connection between total asset turnover ratio and the degree of profitability.

3.4 The Multiple Regressions Empirical Model

$$LOGPM = \alpha + \beta_1 LITR + \beta_2 LDTR + \beta_3 LTAT + \beta_4 LWCT + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (1.6)$$

Where,

LOGPM = Natural log value of profit margin ratio for Indian oil companies

LITR = Aggregate value of inventory turnover ratio for Indian oil companies from 2010-15.

LDTR = Aggregate value of debtor turnover ratio for Indian oil companies from 2010-15.

LTAT = Aggregate value of total assets turnover ratio for Indian oil companies from 2010-15.

LWCT = Aggregate value of working capital turnover ratio for Indian oil companies from 2010-15.

α = Intercepts, β = parameters, E = Error

4. RESULTS AND LEARNING INSIGHTS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table-1 presents the descriptive result of several ratios of Indian oil companies from 2010 to 2015. It contains profitability ratio i.e. profit margin, activity ratio i.e. inventory turnover ratio, debtor turnover ratio, and working capital turnover, and total assets turnovers have been employed in this paper to measure the relationship between activity ratio and profitability of the company. Following statistics i.e. mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis has been used to determine values for activity and profitability ratio. The descriptive statistics shows that over the period under study, the financial ratios measured by Inventory turnover ratio (ITR), Debtors' turnover ratio (DTR), Working capital turnover ratio (WCT) and Total assets turnover ratio (TATR) have a positive mean value which ranges from 10.999 total assets turnover to 1117.506 in working capital turnover ratio.

	Debtor Turnover Ratio (DTR)	Inventory Turnover Ratio (ITR)	Profit Margin (PM)	Total Assets Turnover (TAT)	Working Capital Turnover (WCT)
Mean	144.3219	38.62300	0.593990	10.99909	1117.506
Median	144.1219	35.01053	0.622500	11.66417	1181.188
Maximum	154.5103	52.90828	0.677659	12.40209	1322.562
Minimum	130.0233	28.30310	0.467925	8.813304	809.6370
Std. Dev.	9.673601	10.99418	0.082387	1.510863	214.4081
Skewness	-0.456649	0.354277	-0.661861	-0.570952	-0.504954
Kurtosis	1.991567	1.410755	2.094695	1.727783	1.738584
Jarque-Bera	0.385636	0.630781	0.535795	0.608850	0.543976
Probability	0.824632	0.729504	0.764986	0.737547	0.761863
Sum	721.6094	193.1150	2.969948	54.99546	5587.530
Sum Sq. De	374.3142	483.4876	0.027150	9.130824	183883.4

4.2 Checking the Data for Stationary

Degree of profitability by taking profit margin ratio, in order to test whether the series is stationary or not, the plots of auto correlation functions (ACF) were used and were found to be within confidence intervals. To further establish stationary, a unit root stationary test Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation and Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin test statistic was carried out and followings values were obtained.

4.2.1 Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic:

Table-2 Null Hypothesis: LOG_PM_ has a unit root problem

			t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic			-1.381184	0.5367
Test critical values:	1% level		-4.582648	
	5% level		-3.320969	
	10% level		-2.801384	
*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.				

*: Bold letter indicates significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% level of significance.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation¹

The result for stationary data are contains in Table 2. The computed ADF test-statistic (-1.38) is larger than the critical values - ‘tau’ (-2.80, -3.32, -4.58 at 10 per cent, 5 per cent, 1 per cent significant level, respectively), therefore we can reject null hypothesis ‘series has a unit root problem’. It means the profitability of given series doesn’t have a unit root problem and the data series is a stationary series at 1 per cent, 10 per cent and 5 per cent significant level.

4.2.2 Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin test statistic

Table-3 Null Hypothesis: LOG_PM_ is stationary

			LM-Stat.
Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin test statistic			0.406062
Asymptotic critical values*:	1% level		0.739000
	5% level		0.463000
	10% level		0.347000
*Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin (1992, Table 1)			
Residual variance (no correction)			0.078648
HAC corrected variance (Bartlett kernel)			0.164456

*: Bold letter indicates significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% level of significance.

The result for stationary data are contains in Table 3. The computed KPSS test-statistic (0.4060) is between the critical values - (0.3470, 0.4630, 0.7290) at 10 per cent, 5 per cent, 1 per cent significant level, respectively), therefore we can accept null hypotheses ‘data series is

stationary'. It means the profitability of given series doesn't have a unit root problem and the data series is a stationary series at 10 per cent significant level.

4.3 Result of Multiple Regressions Empirical Model

Table-4Least squares multiple regression model

Dependent Variable: LOGPM				
White heteroskedasticity-consistent standard errors & covariance				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-7.03E-05	8.57E-05	-0.820452	0.4580
LITR	-0.118629	0.079463	-1.492886	0.2098
LDTR	-0.117986	0.140540	-0.839515	0.4484
LTAT	1.858856	0.420609	4.419441	0.0115*
LWCT	-0.564805	0.209518	-2.695732	0.0543*
R-squared	0.297029	Mean dependent var		-0.293974
Adjusted R-squared	0.284057	S.D. dependent var		0.297454
S.E. of regression	0.022930	Akaike info criterion		-3.412557
Sum squared resid	0.002103	Schwarz criterion		-3.302988
Log likelihood	24.85651	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-3.649007
F-statistic	335.5587	Durbin-Watson stat		2.057273
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000026			

*: According to literature on the profitability, slope of the series of various indicators should be negative. Bold letter indicates significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% level of significance.

Results & Analyses

Based on the multiple regression result presented in table 4, it was clear that total assets turnover ratio and working capital turnover ratio were regressed against the profitability of Indian oil companies from 2010-15. Inventory turnover ratio and Debtor turnover ratio were found to be non-significant against the profitability. The inventory turnover ratio has a negative relationship with the profitability. The t-calculated and p value of inventory turnover ratio is -1.49 and 0.209. Which indicates that the inventory turnover ratio of Indian oil companies could not statistically significant affect the profitability of oil companies in India. So, we accept the null hypotheses that there is no statically significant relationship between Inventory turnover ratio and the profitability. This means that a change in inventory practically have no effect on Indian oil company profitability. Our findings for insignificant and negative relationship of Inventory turnover ratio is also confirms the findings of Lazaridis and Tryfonidis (2006). They had found insignificant and a negative relationship between inventory and profitability.

The Debtor turnover ratio has a negative relationship with the profitability. The t-calculated and p value of inventory turnover ratio is -0.83 and 0.448. Which indicates that the Debtor turnover ratio of Indian oil companies could not statistically significant affect the profitability of oil

companies in India. So, we accept the null hypotheses that there is no statically significant relationship between Debtor turnover ratio and the profitability. This means that a change in debtors practically have no effect on Indian oil company profitability. Our findings for insignificant and a negative relationship of debtor turnover ratio is also confirms the findings of Dave (2012).

The total assets turnover ratio has a positive relationship with the profitability. The t-calculated and p value of inventory turnover ratio is 4.41 and 0.011. Which indicates that the total assets turnover ratio of Indian oil companies could statistically significant affect the profitability of oil companies in India. So, we reject the null hypotheses that there is no statically significant relationship between total asset turnover ratio and the profitability and accept the alternate hypotheses H_4 that there is a positive significant connection between total asset turnover ratio and the degree of profitability. This means that a change in total assets practically have an effect on Indian oil company profitability. Our findings for significant and a positive relationship of total assets turnover ratio is not confirms the findings of Dave (2012).

The working capital turnover ratio has a negative relationship with the profitability. The t-calculated and p value of inventory turnover ratio is -2.69 and 0.053. Which indicates that the working capital turnover ratio of Indian oil companies could statistically significant affect the profitability of oil companies in India. So, we reject the null hypotheses that there is no statically significant relationship between working capital turnover ratio and the profitability and accept the alternate hypotheses H_3 that there is a negative significant connection between working capital turnover ratio and the degree of profitability. This means that a change in working capital practically have an effect on Indian oil company profitability.

5. CONCLUSION

After conducting a comprehensive activity ratio analysis of IOCL, BPCL, HPCL, and CAIRN, we arrived at the following conclusions: inventory turnover ratio of Indian oil companies has a negative but statistically insignificant effect on the profitability of oil companies in India. So that Indian oil companies should better utilize their inventory. Debtor turnover ratio has a negative but statistically insignificant affect the profitability of oil companies in India, which shows that these companies does not efficiently used their sales to generate earning and have outperformed other companies. They have also generated less account receivables. Total assets turnover ratio of Indian oil companies has a positive statistically significant affect with the profitability of oil companies in India. Which means, Indian oil companies effetely used their assets to generate profit. Working capital turnover ratio of Indian oil companies has a negative statistically significant affect with the profitability of oil companies in India. Which shows that these companies does not efficiently used their working capital to generate earning. Indian oil companies should re-invest their margins back into the business and get rid of their liabilities and increase income by paying out less from the profits. Indian oil companies should also try

different strategies offering more options to investors to try and generate more revenue, such as bond options and possibly selling more shares of the company. We recommend trying and promoting more bonds and decreasing the amount of stocks out there on the market to increase the price earnings of each share. We also recommend that selected Indian oil companies should try to take more control of their costs in order to raise their profit margin and be competitive and Indian oil's companies allocate some funds to improve their image in the next couple years to generate more sales. Finally, we suggest maintaining the efforts they are currently using because it is proved to be very successful to them and they are selling their product at a faster pace. Indian oil companies should also try and boost the asset turnover by using different promotional strategies and make sure the equipment and capital are helping you generate more revenue than to spend on repairs.

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